

NOTES

Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Sulphathiazole Complexes with Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , La^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Y^{3+}

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In the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphathiazole with various trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The Corning Model 12, a precision research pH meter with combined, glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. Both electrodes dip into the titrating mixture, without vitiating any results. The changes in the pH meter readings can be recorded with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphathiazole was prepared by dissolving 10 gms of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) in about 50 ml of absolute ethanol. To this was added equimolar quantity of sulphathiazole. This reaction mixture was refluxed in a water bath for about 2 hrs. After cooling, the solution was filtered to get the crude product which was repeatedly crystallised from 75 : 25 percent D.M.F./ H_2O mixture to get an analytically pure compound. The m.p., observed was 251°. The purity of the ligand has also been ascertained by the elemental analysis. Observed : C, 58.62% ; H, 3.63% ; N, 10.24% ; S, 15.59%. Calculated : C, 58.54% ; H, 3.90% ; N, 10.24% ; S, 15.61%.

The dioxan used for experimental work was purified by the method described by Vogel². Double distilled water was used throughout the investigation. The titrations were carried out in the inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions. Metal ion solutions of yttrium, gadolinium and neodymium were prepared by taking the metal nitrates of A.R. grade. Metal ion solutions of dysprosium, praseodymium and lanthanum were prepared by taking the metal carbonates of A.R. grade. All metal nitrates and carbonates were supplied by S.D. Lab. Chem. Industry, Bombay. The metal nitrates were converted to the

carbonates and these were further converted to the corresponding perchlorates by using A.R. grade perchloric acid. The metal ion solutions were standardised complexometrically³ by EDTA titrations. The strength of sodium hydroxide used was 1.04M.

The experimental details and computational methods are same as described earlier in our communication⁴. The following solutions were prepared, the total volume in each case being 40 ml. These were then titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.04M), solution.

- (i) 5 ml of (0.16M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml of dioxan.
- (ii) 5 ml of (0.16M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + requisite amount of ligand accurately weighed to give 0.004M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.
- (iii) 5 ml of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml of metal salt (0.008M) solution in (0.16M) HClO_4 + the requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

The absence of any significant drift in pH of the solution even after 2 hrs indicated that the ligand used does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described.

In the ligand the phenolic (OH) group takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each molecule is one.

The titration curves obtained from solutions (i) and (ii) were used for finding out the \bar{n}_A values for the various 'B' values (pH meter readings). The \bar{n}_A values were then plotted against the corresponding 'B' values to obtain a formation curve. This was found to extend over a range of $0.07 < \bar{n}_A < 1.0$ $pK_1^{\bar{n}}$ was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexion

equilibria. From these formation curves, the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by the half integral method. Since the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values for Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , was found to be less than 1.78 log units, the same were calculated by least square method. The standard deviation of $\log K$ values was calculated by the standard method⁵ and was found to be 0.02. The limits of error were also calculated⁵ and were found to be ± 0.02 .

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of the trivalent metal chelates was found to be

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

$t = 25^\circ$		$\mu = 0.1$					
Cations	H^+	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	La^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Y^{3+}
$\log K_1$	7.97	8.11	7.9	7.65	7.08	6.02	4.8
$\log K_2$	—	5.98	—	—	5.18	—	3.8

* For proton association (H^+), K_1 corresponds to the species LH , while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 , respectively.

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Studies on the Complexes of Platinum Group Metals with Nicotinamide and Brucine

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THE present communication reports the complex formation of platinum group metals with nicotinamide and brucine which finds little mention in the existing chemical literature.

Experimental

Na_2PtCl_4 , Na_2PdCl_4 , Na_2OsCl_6 , Na_2IrCl_6 and $RhCl_3 \cdot H_2O$ (Johnson Matthey), nicotinamide (B.D.H) and brucine (Whiffen) were used in these experiments.

The metal-nicotinamide (or metal-brucine) complexes were prepared by mixing the ethanolic solutions of the metal salt and the ligand with vigorous shaking when a precipitate was obtained. It was washed several times with ethanol and subsequently with hexane and then dried *in vacuo*. The complexes were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents making their crystallization impossible.

The complexes were microanalysed for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and chlorine. The hydrogen analyses are somewhat high because of the ready absorption of water by these complexes during the process of analysis. The molar conductance was measured on a Philips conductivity bridge model PR 9500 in dimethyl sulphoxide using $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions Table 1.

The infra red spectra of the complexes were recorded on a 'Perkin-Elmer' model '621' ir machine in the frequency range of $4000-600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in KBr pellets. The magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Faraday balance at B.H.U., Varanasi. The thermograms were run on a manual apparatus at G. N. D. University, Amritsar and the diffused transmittance spectra were taken in nujol mull on NIR-vis-DMR-21 apparatus at RSIC, Madras.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis of the complexes shows that Pd(II) and Pt(II) interact with nicotinamide to give complexes with the composition, $Pd(\text{Nicotinamide})_2Cl_2$ and $Pt(\text{Nicotinamide})_2Cl_2$. The molar conductance¹ shows that they are non-electrolytes.

Nicotinamide absorbs at 3360, 3160 (NH bands), 1670 (CO stretching), 1610 and 1595 (C=C and C=N stretchings), 1115 (ν_{CN}) and at 1020 and 696 cm^{-1} (pyridine ring vibrations). The CO frequency goes down by $10-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on complexation. The $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ go to 1600, 1586, 1585 and 1525 cm^{-1} in Pd and Pt complexes respectively. The pyridine ring vibrations occur at 1020 and 682; and at 1000 and 640 cm^{-1} in Pd and Pt complexes respectively and show a great decrease in intensity. The NH bands at 3360 and 3160 cm^{-1} show splitting into several peaks in the two complexes. These changes in the ir absorptions show that the coordination of platinum and palladium occurs through the oxygen of the carbonyl group and the heterocyclic nitrogen. Thus both palladium and platinum are hexacoordinated in these complexes with nicotinamide.

The alkaloid, brucine forms 1:1 complexes with Pd(II), Pt(II), Os(IV) and Ir(IV) chlorides. $RhCl_3$ forms a 2:1 complex. The complexes are